

APPLYING SYSTEMIC DESIGN ON HUMAN PROCESSES

A FIRST APPROACH TO SUSTAINABLE ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

Daniela Restrepo Ortiz

Industrial Designer MSc. in Eco-design

Co-creator Life Jam – Design Network for Sustainable Humanity

✉ daniela.restrepo.ortiz@gmail.com

✉ lifejammers@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The following research seeks to understand how disciplines such as Systemic Design can be applied to human relations in order to establish the concepts of a new social phenomenon. Its purpose is to activate a new interdisciplinary culture, to create a network of knowledge, to outline a dialogue between the diverse disciplines that depend on each other to provide more sustainable solutions to the world's complex issues. This ongoing research seeks to analyze how the study of human dimensions from different areas can be used to design strategies that can socially innovate. The research itself represents a backup study to the development and design of integrated and systemic experiences. By merging design with psychological branches such as Logotherapy, we will provide an example of possible applications of the theory.

KEYWORDS: *Systemic Design, Logotherapy, Sustainability, and Anthrop-o-systems.*

INTRODUCTION

Designers continue to approach an object, a space or even a service, in an attempt to solve specific problems. What if a more integrated praxis of design and emotion is missing? Can the current design practices be integrated into other fields of action? Nowadays, society's most complex issues related to education, fair trade, sanitation, pollution, human rights, climate change and others, continue to grow (especially in developing countries). Design processes can constitute an integrative experience that leads to the resolution of such conflicts and the improvement of human conditions. Therefore, it becomes vital to understand where design is leading to and how it can serve to provoke real change.

SYSTEMIC DESIGN

The Politecnico di Torino (Italy) has recently proved that **Systemic Design** shows a new perspective towards more sustainable solutions. **Sustainability** is understood in this paper as the by-product of diverse strategies (social, economic, commercial, political, and others) that project the elements of a system in such a way that it becomes self-sufficient, with a

tendency to zero emissions. From that perspective, design practitioners have witnessed a drastic change in the role that design can now play in society. Italian designer and professor, Luigi Bistagnino projects sustainability from a productive, territorial and cultural viewpoint. He specifically describes this branch of design as follows:

“Systemic Design projects the relations between the components that generate a system (...) gives value to the *identity* and local resources producing development and welfare both for individuals and collectivities. The relationships between each component are generated through interaction to create balance and the result is the quality of the created system.” (Bistagnino, 2009)

Concepts such as *identity* and *human behavior* become essential in the analysis of the components that generate a system. Granting value to human beings and placing them at the center of the projects, not as the main and most important actor, but as one that is able to integrate the resources, cultural aspects and other elements of its environment, in order to connect and recover what is now being wasted.

Systemic Design has been suggested as a term for this emerging movement in design, also known as Systems Oriented Design or Whole Systems Design. Academies such as the Oslo School of Architecture and Design (Oslo, Norway) have been setting up periodic events and workshops involving students

Figure 1. Systemic Design (Bistagnino, 2009)

and teachers in the discussion of new strategies and tools regarding this topic. One of the most recent conclusions of these meetings was:

“What binds systems related theories and practices together with design approaches may be the desire to reintroduce systems approaches with design toward a more effective integrated praxis (...). This implies the reshaping and design of systems approaches and the related practices so that they are better integrated into design processes.” (Oslo School of Architecture & Design, 2013)

The transition from a linear thinking process to a systemic one has already been made not only by designers but by other professionals as well. Even though one of the fathers of system's theory is Ludwin von Bertalanfy, throughout history, characters involved in the study of human evolution have applied a more integral approach in their areas of study. Such is the case of **Urie Bronfenbrenner** in psychology and **Ezio Manzini** in the

fields of design and social innovation. Many other important authors have applied systemic thinking in the creation of commercial and economical strategies such as **Gunter Pauli** (seen in his theory on the Blue Economy), and in philosophical, ecological and spiritual fields such as **Ken Wilber** (which we will look at later on).

URIE BRONFENBRENNER AND THE ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS THEORY

This American psychologist was known for developing the Ecological Systems Theory. Bronfenbrenner's theory was ecological for he added biological influences to his studies. He approached human development as a life-spent system from childhood to adulthood. The theory states that development reflects the influence of mini environmental systems. (Olson, 2007).

Figure 2. Interpretation of Eric Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory. There are five environmental systems: 1) Microsystems, 2) Mesosystems, 3) Exosystems, 4) Macrosystems and 5) Cronosystems. These systems are embedded into each other and get bigger as they branch out. They help to emphasize how important environmental factors are (Olson, 2007).

The Ecological System theory shows that it is important to understand the life styles of individuals and their development because it helps to explain human interaction and how people's lives and events are influenced by their surroundings. Bronfenbrenner's theory was applied in the area of education and in the analysis of childhood development, opening the path to new ways of connecting systemic thinking to the understanding of human behaviors.

FROM ECOLOGICAL VIEWPOINTS TO PRODUCTIVE PROCESSES

Furthermore, in business management, productive processes and within the industrial field, systemic approaches have been applied to design new methodologies. The **Product-service system (PSS)**, also known as a function-oriented business model, is a model that aims to provide sustainable consumption and production. A Product-Service System is created when a stakeholder (firm, enterprise, etc.) offers a mix of both products and services, in contrast to the traditional focus on products (Cooka, 2006).

Social sciences, business, design and technology gave birth to what is now known as Service Design. From these areas, several tools were taken to contribute to Industrial Design, which has seen the development and establishment of several methods and techniques over the years. This period has witnessed the birth of new tools (specific to the Service Design practice) that are able to reach a higher level of complexity and to communicate the immaterial aspects of a project such as time and experience (Tassi, 2009). The similarity between systems approach and Service Design lies within the actors' involvement in service creation, development and delivery, in terms of their roles and resources. Describing a system means identifying the main figures involved, becoming more deeply acquainted with the actors' features and the existing relations between them. It specifies their activities and aims to take part in the service process (Tassi, 2009). Therefore, the two approaches do not compete against each other; instead, they are meant to co-develop new creative structures especially to project social innovation programs.

EZIO MANZINI AND DESIS

The collaboration between systems approach and Service Design can be seen in DESIS (Design for Social Innovation towards Sustainability). This is a network of design labs and design-oriented organizations, actively involved in promoting and supporting sustainable change. Ezio Manzini, one of Italy's greatest social innovators and president of the DESIS network, established what could be the building blocks of a new way of doing design (and to conceive human relations). He invites designers to change their focus of observation in order to become interpreters of human phenomena. According to Manzini, users should not be seen as bearers of necessities but as bearers of capacities: designers are in charge of observing

society **when** and **where** new organizations that construct new ways of **being** or **doing** are born. These moments are the result of a creative moment that transforms into a valuable entrepreneurship initiative (Manzini, 2010).

FIRST APPROACH TO SUSTAINABLE ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems theory and projects such as DESIS, clearly demonstrate that applying systemic theory to social, productive, economic, commercial and environmental processes *can* promote the creation of innovative solutions. Brand new ideas are waiting to be explored and now designers have a chance to project their creativity integrally.

So, what about those designers concerned with the development of new social practices that can lead to measurable impacts on communities? Manzini proves that if human relations could be interpreted not only as common and usual behaviors, but also as flows of information, transmission of messages, signals and more, designers could be approaching a new area of intervention in social innovation. Human systems or *Anthrop-o-systems* (as they will be referred to in the present paper) are made up of a series of elements that not only refer to an existing being, but also to a series of inputs and outputs that are constantly coming in and out of every individual. Such is the case of a community in which a group of individuals exchanges inputs and outputs. Nonetheless, a community is placed in a certain locality: a city, a country, a continent and so on. Truth is, there is more to the matter than meets the eye: philosopher Ken Wilber has studied the complexity of a part and a whole. One of Wilber's key concepts is to study and categorize items in terms of their nature as holons, a term derived from the writings of Arthur Koestler. He noticed that every entity and concept shares a dual role: both being autonomous, self-sufficient units (whole entity) unto themselves, and also a part of one (or more) other wholes (Koestler, 1967). An example of this is the way in which a cell in an organism is both a whole as a cell and at the same time a part of another whole, which is the organism. Everything from qualks, to matter, to energeu, to ideas can be perceived in this way.

SYSTEMIC DESIGN AND ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

When analyzing the main tenants and the philosophy of Systemic Design from the perspective of Prof. Bistagnino (Politecnico di Torino), certain similarities regarding the subject of sustainable Anthrop-o-systems became evident. Each one of the following principles has an application in human relations as well. There are five main principles to design according to this systemic approach. Next to each one of them, a parallel with Anthrop-o-systems will be made.

1) A system's outputs and/or wastes have to be transformed into inputs and/or resources of another system. (Bistagnino, 2009)

This means that in order to develop sustainably, everything that comes in and out of a human being needs to be transformed into what comes in or out of another human being. Individuals need to be more aware of the fact that everything is entirely recyclable: not only their waste but also their experiences, their words and everything involved in their daily activities. From the material to the immaterial (from an object to an emotion).

2) A system has to be generated from inner and outer relationships that contribute to the system. (Bistagnino, 2009)

An Anthrop-o-system needs to be generated from the inner relationships of the individual as well as the outer relationships that surround him/her. The relationship between individuals and society should work in the same way, for individuals and societies are both holons within a bigger holon.

3) A system needs to be self-generated, meaning that it has to sustain from its automatic self-production, defining its own action and coevolving as a unit. (Bistagnino, 2009)

When coevolving as an automatic self-produced unit, an Anthrop-o-system is able to transform and impact its own community when relating collectively with other Anthrop-o-systems. This means that design practitioners have the challenging task of scaling-up human resources and all that this implies.

4) Acting locally: The local environment is fundamental because there has to be a valorization of human, material and cultural local resources that work to solve social, cultural and ethical problems (Bistagnino, 2009).

An Anthrop-o-system needs to take advantage of the closest resources at hand, meaning that it will not only rescue the identity and authenticity of what is local, but it will also generate a cultural statement through its interaction with the context. There is a need to focus on local specificities when working with Anthrop-o-systems rescuing not only fundamental aspects such as language, but also local expressions, folklore, cultural assets and more.

5) Human beings have to be at the center of the project, co-evolving with other fluxes and connected with the system and local environment in a social, cultural and ethical manner. (Bistagnino, 2009)

Once again, it becomes evident that humans need to be placed at the center of the project itself. This means that human activity (including its material and immaterial processes) needs to be analyzed, decomposed and represented in fluxes that show interconnectedness and interdependence between each particular element.

What would an Anthrop-o-system look like according to these principles and applying systemic theories? In order to represent one of these systems, *Human Needs* and *Human-scale Development* established by Manfred Max-Neef were taken into account. They were chosen for this analysis because they are few, finite and classifiable as well as constant through all human cultures and across historical time periods. What changes over time and between cultures, are the strategies by which these needs are satisfied (Max-Neef, 1989).

Figure 3. Anthrop-o-system. The diagram was developed according to Max- Neef and his classification of the fundamental human needs: subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, leisure, creation, identity and freedom. Needs are also defined according to the existential categories of being, having, doing and interacting. Every human activity is influenced by these dimensions.

An Anthrop-o-system could become a more widely-used tool if design practitioners interpret it not only as an element of any system but also as a holon (applying Wilber's concept): a whole system part of another system, in particular, if they are creating experiences that relate to social and emotional factors. The following diagram explains how Systemic Design was used for the planning of an After School Program. It was part of a tendering process in a project for public schools in Bogota (Colombia) that has not yet been approved.

The inner relations of this specific Anthrop-o-system are not only regulated within each individual, but the interaction between different stakeholders begins and starts to create a network of collaborative education. This means that the outputs of a stakeholder could become the input of another actor; the community in which the program is implemented becomes a local provider of resources as well as the receptor of those inputs. Even though the project has not been executed, the Systemic Design approach has contributed to create unique methodologies that can trigger a positive change and evolution of the education paradigm in Colombia.

The graphic representation of this project is similar to that which is used as a tool in Service Design: a blueprint. The **service blueprint** is a technique used for service innovation. Lynn Shostack, a bank executive, first described this technique in a 1984 Harvard Business Review. The blueprint shows processes within a company, divided into different components, which are separated by lines. The traditional blueprints (as used in disciplines like product design, architecture and

engineering) are instruments for building, standardizing, communicating, planning and sharing a project (Shostack, 1984). While analyzing how blueprints are used in Service Design, it becomes obvious that they give only a partial representation of how a service works: they provide a detailed visualization of the actions and processes, without looking at the motivational and emotional sides (Tassi, 2009).

INTERVENTION OF LOGOTHERAPY IN ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

In order to apply systemic theories in human matters, it becomes necessary to link this with other anthropological, sociological and especially psychological studies that have been performed. Logotherapy or Existential Analysis (LTEA), established by psychiatrist and neurologist Viktor Emil Frankl (1905-1997) in the 1930s, is an internationally acknowledged meaning-centered approach to psychotherapy. There is a fundamental element from Logotherapy that may be interpreted as a tool for providing sustainability to an Anthrop-o-system. This is the concept of **self-distancing** which gives human beings the capacity to distance themselves from their own heritage, conditioning or whatever else influences them to act in a particular way.

“According to LTEA humans are not fully subject to conditions but are basically free to decide and capable of taking their stance towards internal (psychological) and external (biological

Figure 4. Application of Systemic Design in the planning of an after-school program for public schools of Bogotá (Colombia).

and social) conditions. Freedom is here defined as the space to shape one's own life within the limits of the given possibilities.” (Batthyany, 2010)

Self-distancing implies the development of meta-cognitive skills: a learner's automatic awareness of their own knowledge and their ability to understand, control, and manipulate their own cognitive and emotional processes (Martínez, 2007). It means to be able to act differently to the direction in which the feelings manipulate an individual. That is, opposing what the person is feeling not to fight against those feelings, but to adapt to different perspectives. Therefore, self-distancing becomes the means through which an individual can actually relate to what surrounds him/her: a situation, a person, a feeling, or a message. It means that if self-distancing becomes a response to several stimuli, the inputs and outputs of an Anthrop-o-system *can* actually be controlled or measured by the individual that produces, transmits and receives them.

The following Figure shows the intervention of self-distancing in two specific activities: talking and listening. They are both satisfiers of the human need for participation from the interaction categories of being (Max-Neef, 1989). The communication skills of an individual unable to self-distance from his inner (and external) conditions are going to be limited. Nonetheless, the individual that is able to self-distance from what he hears (leaving aside his inner emotions, feelings, conditionings etc.) will be able to interact more efficiently.

The example makes clear that both spoken and heard messages become inputs and outputs within these two Anthrop-o-systems interacting in a conversation. The quality of both inputs and outputs, depends on the will of the subject to self-distance or not.

CONCLUSIONS

The world in which designers create these days is full of challenges that go beyond the regular design praxis. This task is not easy, as designers need to assume the role of *connectors* and “sponges” absorbent and permeable to all sorts of theories. The application of combinatorial thinking is a requirement now, and design-oriented academies (as well as other educational institutions) need to provide such tools and knowledge.

Systems theory and most importantly Systemic Design can be used to project experiences that give rise to human beings' need to effectively connect and relate to others. This might be the key to solve many of our current global crises and, if used well, it could become a tool for communities to develop social strategies that can lead to real change and improvement of life conditions. It is evident that Anthrop-o-systems can have an important role in social innovation if understood and applied as a method to connect and communicate. Linking solutions to emotions that can be regulated by self-distancing *could* make a difference. The unique combination between Logotherapy and Anthrop-o-systems may guarantee an important and innovative progress in Systemic Design approaches.

Since Systemic Design gives us the chance to decompose the parts of a whole and, at the same time, merge these elements together in a web of knowledge, it represents a basic tool for social entrepreneurs and it should be used in the planning, development and implementation of any kind of program. We hope that, this will provide people with solutions that they can use to generate positive change. When we begin to understand social matters as whole and not as independent issues that cannot be solved collectively we *will* make a difference.

Figure 5. Intervention of self-distancing in two activities: talking and listening.

REFERENCES

- Bistagnino, L (2009) Design Sistemico – Progettare la sostenibilità produttiva e ambientale. In: Slow Food Editore (Ed.), Bra, Italy, 18-200
- Capra, F. (2010) The web of life - A new synthesis of mind and matter. In: Harper Collins (Ed.), Great Britain, 17-216
- Cooka, M.B. (2006). The Transfer and Application of Product Service Systems: From Academia to UK Manufacturing Firms. In: Journal of Cleaner Production (Elsevier Ltd). Retrieved April 15, 2014 from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652606000771>
- García, C. (2007) La humanidad posible. In: Lag Ediciones (Ed.), Mexico D.F, Mexico, 75-154
- Koestler, A. (1967). Retrieved April 15, 2014 from <http://www.panarchy.org/koestler/holon.1969.html>
- Lawrence, R. (2004) Housing and Health: From Interdisciplinary Principles to Transdisciplinary Research and Practice. In: Futures (Ed.), 487-502.
- Martínez, E. (2007) Psicoterapia y sentido de vida. In: Herder (Ed.), Bogotá, Colombia.
- Max-Neef, M., Elizalde A., Hopenhayn, M. (1989). Human scale development: conception, application and further reflections. New York: Apex. Chpt. 2. "Development and Human Needs", p. 18.
- Olson, D. (2007) Human development. In: McGraw-Hill Learning Solutions (Ed.), Dubuque, United States.
- Pauli, G. (2010) La economía azul—10 años, 100 innovaciones, 100 millones de empleos. In: Metatemas (Ed.), Mexico D. F, Mexico, 351-354
- Service Design Tools: Communication Methods supporting design process. Tassi R. (2009). Retrieved April 19, 2014 from <http://www.servicedesigntools.org/taxonomy/term/22>
- Shostack, G. L. (1984). Designing Services that Deliver. Harvard Business Review, vol. 62, no. 1 January - February 1984, pp. 133-139. Retrieved April 19, 2014 from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Service_blueprint
- The second episode of Relating Systems Thinking and Design Thinking Symposium (RSD2) held at The Oslo School of Architecture and Design (AHO) in October 2013. AHO – Oslo School of Architecture & Design Oslo, Norway 9th-11th October 2013
- The Blurring of Design Boundaries (2010). Retrieved Oct 7, 2013 from <http://www.northumbria.ac.uk/sd/academic/scd/research/themes/makingconnections/casestudies/2349282/>
- Viktor Frankl Institut. (2010). Retrieved Dic 15, 2013 from <http://logotherapy.univie.ac.at/e/logotherapy.html>